

Review On : HYDROALCOHOLIC EXTRACTION OF Ruta graveolens L.

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Abstract

Ruta graveolens L., popularly known as SATABA(in marathi) is a multipurpose herb belonging to family Rutaceae. It is a rich source of secondary metabolites mainly: coumarins, alkaloids, volatile oils, flavonoids, and phenolic acids. It has been used abundantly worldwide due to its diverse medicinal properties. Extract and essential oil obtained from this plant species have been shown to possess various pharmacological activities including contraceptive, anti-inflammatory, antimicrobial, antipyretic, antioxidant, analgesic, antihyperglycemic, free radical scavenging, hypotensive, antiviral, and antiplasmodial effects. In vitro assays performed with human cell lines have indicated the anticancer potential of furanoacridones and acridone alkaloids isolated from *R. graveolens*. In vitro approaches have been carried out for rapid clonal multiplication of *R. graveolens*. Application of hairy root culture has effectively observed to be beneficial for enhanced production of bioactive compounds from this plant species. A review of literature suggests that it is an interesting plant species to pharmaceutical industry due to its potential to produce several pharmacological effects.

Keywords: *Ruta graveolens L.*, Rutin, Quercetin, Flavonoids, Phytochemicals, extraction method

INTRODUCTION :

- *Ruta graveolens*, commonly known as rue, common rue or herb-of-grace, is a species of the genus *Ruta* grown as an ornamental plant and herb. It is native to the Balkan Peninsula. It is grown throughout the world in gardens, especially for its bluish leaves, and sometimes for its tolerance of hot and dry soil conditions. It is also cultivated as a culinary herb, and to a lesser extent as an insect repellent and incense. Rue is used as a traditional flavouring in Greece and other Mediterranean countries.
- In Istria (a region spanning Croatia and Slovenia), and in Northern Italy, it is used to give a special flavour to grappa/raki and most of the time a little branch of the plant can be found in the bottle. This is called *grappa alla ruta*.
- Seeds can be used for porridge.
- The bitter leaf can be added to eggs, cheese, fish, or mixed with damson plums and wine to produce a meat sauce.
- In Italy in Friuli-Venezia Giulia, the young branches of the plant are dipped in a batter, deep-fried in oil, and consumed with salt or sugar. They are also used on their own to aromatise a specific type of omelette.
- Used in Old World beers as flavouring ingredient.
- The rue that is widespread in Ethiopian culture is a different species, *R. chalapensis*.

Rue is also grown as an ornamental plant, both as a low hedge and so the leaves can be used in nosegays.

Most cats dislike the smell of it, and it can, therefore, be used as a deterrent to them (see also *Plectranthus caninus*).^[citation needed]

Caterpillars of some subspecies of the butterfly *Papilio machaon* feed on rue, as well as other plants. The caterpillars of *Papilio xuthus* also feed readily on it.

In Sephardic Jewish tradition, ruda is believed to possess protective qualities against malevolent forces, particularly the evil eye. It is often placed near vulnerable individuals, such as newborns, children, and mothers, to ward off evil. Beyond its symbolic significance, ruda is valued for its medicinal properties. When combined with sugar, it is traditionally used to soothe eye discomfort and alleviate the symptoms of a mild cold. Additionally, inhaling ruda is thought to mitigate the effects of shock.

Ruda's significance in Sephardic Jewish culture also extends to religious practices. During Yom Kippur, a Jewish holiday marked by fasting, Sephardic synagogues often pass ruda among congregants to revitalise them.

Beyond the Sephardic tradition, Hasidic Jews also recognized the protective qualities of ruda. Hasidic Jews also were taught that rue should be placed into amulets to protect them from epidemics and plagues. Other rely on the works of a famous B who makes mention of the plant "ruda" as an effective device against both black magic and the evil eye.

Plant Profile:

Botanical Name: *Ruta graveolens L.*

Family: Rutaceae

Common Name: Rue, Common Rue, Garden Rue

Habitat: Mediterranean region, Europe, Asia, and North Africa

Plant Description:

- Perennial herb
- Height: 60-120 cm
- Leaves: alternate, bipinnate, 3-5 cm long
- Flowers: small, yellow-green, 5-10 mm diameter
- Fruits: capsule, 5-7 mm long

Pharmacognostic Characteristics:

Macroscopic:

- Root: woody, brown, 1-2 cm diameter
- Stem: woody, brown, 1-2 cm diameter
- Leaves: bipinnate, 3-5 cm long
- Flowers: small, yellow-green

Microscopic:

- Leaf: presence of oil glands, stomata, and trichomes
- Stem: presence of sclerenchyma, xylem, and phloem
- Root: presence of cork cells, sclerenchyma, and xylem

Chemical Constituents:

- Alkaloids: rutinine, graveoline, rutacridone
- Flavonoids: rutin, quercetin, kaempferol
- Coumarins: umbelliferone, scopoletin
- Volatile oils: 2-undecanone, 2-tridecanone

Pharmacological Activities:

- Antimicrobial, Anti-inflammatory, Antioxidant, Antispasmodic, Antiviral, Cytotoxic

COLLECTION OF PLANT MATERIAL:

Rue (*Ruta graveolens L.*; citrus family-Rutaceae) is a hardy, shrub-like evergreen plant.

Rue can grow in almost any conditions, but prefers a semi-sheltered dry environment.

The lower part of the stem is woody, and the leaves are alternate, bluish-green.

They have a strong unpleasant odour and a very bitter disagreeable flavour. The plant blossoms from June–September, with greenish yellow flowers.

Propagation can be carried out by direct seed planting, stem cuttings or root cuttings.

The whole herb is used as for medicinal purposes, the drug consisting of both the fresh and the dried herb.

The shoots are gathered before the plant flowers, with the young shoot tops considered the most valuable.

The volatile oil present in the herb is contained in glands distributed over the whole plant, and is distilled from the fresh herb, as are decoctions and infusions.

Chemical Structure and its mechanism of action:

- Rutin:
- Rutin offers Anti-oxidant properties
- Anti-Viral activity: Rutin can inhibit viral replication by interfering with the viral life cycle, potentially blocking the entry of the virus into the host cells.
- Anti-Inflammatory effects: By reducing inflammation, Rutin may alleviate symptoms associated with rhinovirus infections, such as nasal congestion and sore throat

- Quercetin:
- Anti-inflammatory effects: Known for its Anti-inflammatory and immune-supporting effects. It reduces the production of pro-inflammatory cytokines, helping to alleviate symptoms such as nasal congestion, throat irritation.
- Anti-viral activity: Blocking viral RNA synthesis.
- Anti-oxidant Properties: It neutralizes free radical, reducing oxidative stress and cellular damage associated with viral infections.

Methodology

Solvent Extraction Method

Preparation:

1. Grind dried Ruta graveolns leaves into fine powder.
2. Weigh 100-200g powdered plant material.
3. Pack the powder into a soxhlet thimble.

Soxhlet Extraction:

1. Assemble the sixhlet apparatus.
2. Add 500-1000ml hydroalcoholic solvent to the extraction Chamber.
3. Set the water bath chamber 20-40 degree.
4. Extract for 2-4 hrs for until the solvent chamber is clear

Filteration:

1. Filter the extract using filter paper.
2. Discard the plant residue>

Concentration:

1. Concentrate the extract using a rotatory evaporator or vaccume distillation apparatus.
2. Remove excess solvent

Purification:

1. Use chromatography – TLC(Thin layer chromatography)
Paper Chromatography.

Evaluation Parameter

Flavonoids :

1. Shinoda Test: A small amount of smaple is treated with magnesium turning and concentrated HCL. A Pink or red color indicated the presence of Flavonoids
2. Alkaline reagent test: The Sample is mixed with sodium hydroxide. A yellow colour that changes to red or pink upon acidification suggests flavonoids presence .
3. Lead Acetate test: Sample is mixed with lead acetate solution. A yellow precipitate indicates flavonoids.

Chromatographic Evaluation

<u>Thin Layer Chromatography</u>	<u>Paper Chromatography</u>
<p>PROCEDURE :</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Stationary Phase :Silica gel ➤ Mobile phase :Ethyl acetate :Methanol :Water (7:2:1) ➤ Detection:Chemical Staining 1. Iodine Vapour –Brown or Yellow Spot ➤ Rf value ➤ Visualisation : Note the Rf value and colour of spot. Compare with standard Rutin. 	<p>PROCEDURE:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Stationary Phase : Whatman filter paper ➤ Mobile Phase: Butanol: Acetic acid: Water (4:1:5) ➤ Detection: chemical Staining ➤ 1. Aluminum Chloride: Yellow or Orange Spot ➤ 2. Ferric Chloride : Green or Blue Spot ➤ Visualisation : Note the Rf value and colour of spot. Compare with standard Rutin.

Conclusion:

In conclusion, extracting *Ruta graveolens* (rue) allows us to obtain useful compounds like alkaloids and essential oils, which have medicinal properties such as reducing inflammation, fighting infections, and relieving pain. Common methods for extraction include using alcohol or water. However, while rue can be beneficial, it can also be toxic if taken in large amounts. So, it's important to use the right extraction methods and carefully control the dosage to ensure it is safe and effective for use in medicine.

The extraction of *Ruta graveolens* (commonly known as rue) typically involves the isolation of bioactive compounds from the plant's leaves, stems, or flowers. Various methods, such as solvent extraction (e.g., ethanol, methanol), steam distillation, or cold pressing, can be used depending on the target compounds (e.g., alkaloids, flavonoids, essential oils).

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